

**EVALUATING THE ROLE OF INDIVIDUALISED HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDY
SELECTED FROM THE COMPILED REPERTORY IN CASES OF PATHOLOGICAL
LEUCORRHOEA: AN OPEN LABEL PROSPECTIVE QUASI EXPERIMENTAL STUDY.**

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Abstract-

Background- Pathological leucorrhoea is a prevalent gynaecological disorder affecting women globally, characterized by abnormal vaginal discharge. It is more common in reproductive-age women, particularly in areas with low healthcare access and inadequate cleanliness. The disorder is caused by malfunctioning vaginal mucus glands, leading to increased distress and social embarrassment. A clinical investigation aimed to improve patient outcomes and align homoeopathic treatments with modern medical knowledge. **Methodology-** A clinical trial was conducted at outpatient department of Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be) University Homoeopathic College & Research Centre, Katraj, and Pune Cantonment Bord's Sardar Vallabhai Patel Cantonment General Hospital, focusing on married female patients with leucorrhoea. The study included 50 patients, excluding pregnant women, nursing moms, and those using oral contraceptives. The study used Zomeo Pro software for pathological leucorrhoea-related rubrics and administered homoeopathic remedies. **Result-** The study found that most patients were in the 19-25 age range, with a significant percentage between 25 and 35. The majority were homemakers, with diagnoses for PID, TRICHOMONIASIS, CERVICITIS, BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS, and CANDIDA. After SEPIA, KREOSOTE was given to 12% of patients, and the top three commonly prescribed remedies accounted for 76% of prescriptions. The study concluded that homoeopathic treatment with a compiled repertory is beneficial in treating pathological leucorrhoea. **Conclusion-** The study found that homoeopathic medicines effectively treat pathological leucorrhoea, with the highest-marked medicines reducing vaginal discharge. Further research is needed to compiled more repertories and compare patient distribution.

Keywords –

Pathological leucorrhoea, Homoeopathy, Homoeopathic repertory,

1. INTRODUCTION-

Pathological leucorrhoea, a common gynaecological disorder with major global health implications for women, is typified by abnormal and profuse vaginal discharge. Epidemiologically, women of reproductive age are more likely to report it, especially in areas with low access to healthcare high rates of untreated illnesses and inadequate cleanliness^{1,2}. White discharge is present in about 66.9% of cases, with the bulk of cases occurring in the 23–32 age range. The discharge from pathological leucorrhoea can be yellow, green, or brown. It is also frequently accompanied by an unpleasant odour, vaginal itching, irritation, and discomfort. These symptoms can cause social embarrassment and a significant reduction in a woman's quality of life, as well as distress^{3-5,34}.

Today's woman must take care of her family and provide financial support, which puts a lot of stress on her mental and physical health. She also must support her family in a fast-paced, competitive, and mechanical world. To preserve a healthy pH, stop the entry of microorganisms, and provide lubrication, the female vaginal organ secretes mucus. Excessive mucosal discharge can be attributed to pathological leucorrhoea, which is produced by malfunctioning vaginal mucus glands. The altered function of the

mucus glands will facilitate the invasion and proliferation of microorganisms, not microbes themselves, which is why leucorrhoea occurs⁶⁻¹².

A homoeopathic repertory is an essential resource for practitioners to use when choosing the best treatment following the "similia similibus curentur" concept, which states that "like cures like."¹³⁻¹⁵ Repertories that just address issues related to female reproductive health, such as leucorrhoea, are severely lacking¹⁵⁻¹⁸. It is challenging for practitioners to identify precise treatments for patients due to this lack of specialization of proper rubrics²⁰⁻²³. To address this, specific and comprehensive symptoms about female reproductive health must be added to homoeopathic repertories. By better aligning their therapies with current medical knowledge, practitioners would be able to improve patient outcomes and close the knowledge gap between traditional homoeopathic techniques and contemporary medicine²⁴. A clinical investigation was carried out to close that gap and determine the effectiveness of individualized homoeopathic medicine administered using a set of rubrics gathered from different repertories. Compiled repertory of pathological leucorrhoea is compiled by using following repertory from Kent, Complete, B.T.P.B, Concise, Murphy, Clarke, Boericke, B.S.K, Uterine Minton and Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics & Repertory. The purpose of the compiled repertory is to help in finding the right remedy for a given case. It will reduce the workload of physicians as it is an updated tool, it will reduce the likelihood of physician not going through all the repertories and search the different medicine and rubric of each repertory. This repertory helps to individualize a case and to find the right remedy for the right person. It will also assist in finding small and rarely used remedies and to link unusual symptoms with the appropriate remedy. In many cases we need better definitions of symptoms. It is designed to be a more practical and easier to use refer guide to the homoeopathic Materia-medica.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. Study Settings A clinical trial was carried out in the Repertory department of was conducted at outpatient department of Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed University Homoeopathic College & Research Centre, Katraj, and Pune cantonment Bord's Sardar Vallabhai Patel cantonment general Hospital, OPD, IPD, peripheral OPD. The study concentrated on married patients with leucorrhoea in females in the reproductive age range. To determine the patient's constitution, a unique proforma was utilized.

2.2. Study Subjects Fifty female patients in the reproductive age group from both hospitals who complained of leucorrhoea were included in the study. Among the instances were those with burning, itching, unusual discharge, bad odour, and vaginal discharge. Married women, willing subjects, and OPD patients with diagnosed leucorrhoea were also included in the study. Pregnant women, nursing moms, people with malignancies, people using oral contraceptives, and those with genital tract pathologies that could be fatal were among the exclusion criteria.

2.3. Study Design A prospective, non-randomized, Quasi experimental study research was carried out in 2022–2024. Fifty patients who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study had symptoms of leucorrhoea. Both the peripheral OPDs and the corresponding OPDs monitored the patients. The patient's case determined the length of the follow-up. To create a repertory of pathological leucorrhoea-related rubrics for the study, Zomeo Pro software was utilized as one of the instruments.

2.4. Prescription And Treatment The prescription of homoeopathic remedies is based on the detailed history of each case, including patient and family information. Symptoms are carefully analyzed, with a focus on complaints of leucorrhoea. Medicine was chosen based on the totality of symptoms, complaints, constitutional features, and reportorial totality. The drug was administered in various potencies, doses, and strengths, as per patient requirements. Administration was done through oral and the drug is dispensed in globule and powder form, administered through oral route.

2.5. Outcome assessment The study examines its goals and findings, evaluates each participant's complaints using the ORDIL score and a vaginal assessment form and collects data through interviews and observation to compare improvements before and after treatment.

2.6. Ethical Approval and Clinical Trial Registration

3. RESULT

3.1. **Demographic Finding** The greatest number of patients were in the 19–25 age range, with a sizable percentage falling between the 25 and 35 age range. The study also showed that, with 52% of patients working, 8% being students, 6% being professionals, and 34% being homemakers, the majority of patients were homemakers. The majority of patients received diagnoses for PID, TRICHOMONIASIS, CERVICITIS, BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS, and CANDIDA.

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Age Group	No of patients	Percentage
19-25	12	24%
25-35	25	50%
35-45	7	14%
above 45	6	12%

Figure 1: Pie diagram representing Age-wise distribution of patients

Table 2: Occupation-wise distribution of patients

Occupation	No of Patients	Percentage
Housewife	17	34.00%
Job	26	52.00%
Professional	3	6.00%
Student	4	8.00%

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to Occupation

Table 3: Diagnosis-wise distribution of patients

DIAGNOSIS	Number of patients	Percentage
Bacterial Vaginosis	12	24%
Candida	14	28%
Cervicitis	9	18%
PID	7	14%
Trichomoniasis	8	16%

Figure 3: Distribution of patients according to Occupation

3.2. **Remedy** KREOSOTE was given to 12% of patients after SEPIA to 18% of patients. Between compiled and established repertories, the top three commonly prescribed remedies accounted for 76% of prescriptions, whereas the top three unusual treatments were prescribed to 24% of patients.

Table 4: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

REMEDY	Number of patients	Percentage
ALUMINA	4	8%

AMBRA GRISA	1	2%
AMON CARB	1	2%
ARSENIC ALBUM	1	2%
BORAX	1	2%
CALCAREA CARB	2	4%
GRAPHITIS	2	4%
HYDRASTIS	1	2%
KREOSOTE	6	12%
MERC.SOL	1	2%
NATRUM CARB	1	2%
NATRUM MUR	4	8%
NITRIC ACID	5	10%
PULSATILLA	5	10%
SABINA	1	2%
SEPIA	9	18%
SULPHUR	5	10%

Figure 4: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

3.3. General Health Quality Outcome There was a significant improvement in the Outcome Related to Impact on Daily Living (ORDIL) score following treatment, as evidenced by the score's significant increase. 50% of women had no discharge, 40% had light discharge, and 10% had moderate discharge. The study also discovered a significant difference in vaginal discharge levels before and after therapy. The study concluded that homoeopathic treatment with a compiled repertory is beneficial in treating pathological leucorrhoea.

Table 5: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for ORDIL score before and after the treatment

Variable		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Test statistic and P-value
ORDIL score difference	Negative Ranks	0	0.00	0.00	Z = -6.317
	Positive ranks	50	25.50	1275.00	P-value = 0.00**

3.4. **Statistical analysis:** The study compared the ORDIL scores before and after therapy using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test and Pearson Chi-Square. The null hypothesis was refuted by the results, which revealed a considerable difference. The treatment's success in lowering vaginal discharge was further supported by the chi-square test, which likewise revealed a significant difference. The outcomes imply that the therapy is successful in decreasing vaginal discharge.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of difference in ORDIL score before and after the treatment.

ORDIL Score	N	Mean	Minimum	Median (IQR)	Maximum
Before Treatment	50	-2.44 ± 0.50	-3.0	-2.00(1.00)	-2.0
After Treatment	50	3.36 ± 0.69	2.0	3.00(1.00)	4.0

Figure 6: Median of ORDIL score.

Table 7: Distribution of patients according to improvement level in Outcome Related to Impact on Daily Living (ORDIL).

Improvement	Number of patients	Percentage
MARKED	25	50%
MILD	6	12%
MODERATE	19	38%

Figure 7: Distribution of patients according to improvement level in ORDIL.

Table 8: Vaginal discharge level- distribution of patients before and after treatment.

Vaginal Assessment	Before treatment		After Treatment	
	Number of patients	Percentage	Number of patients	Percentage
No	0	0.00%	25	50.00%
Mild	0	0.00%	20	40.00%
Moderate	28	56.00%	5	10.00%
Severe	22	44.00%	0	0.00%

Figure 8: Vaginal discharge level distribution before and after treatment.

4. DISCUSSION

Pathological leucorrhoea is a prevalent gynaecological condition that affects women of reproductive age worldwide^{25-27,30-32}. The condition is often exacerbated in regions with limited healthcare access, high rates of untreated illnesses, and poor hygiene. The discharge can range in colour from yellow to green or brown and is often accompanied by an unpleasant odour, itching, irritation, and general discomfort. This study aimed to bridge the gap by compiling a comprehensive repertory of symptoms specific to pathological leucorrhoea and assessing the effectiveness of individualized homoeopathic treatments^{28,29,33}. The clinical trial was conducted at outpatient department of Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed University Homoeopathic College & Research Centre, Katraj and Pune Cantonment Board's Sardar Vallabhai Patel Cantonment General Hospital, targeting married women of reproductive age suffering from leucorrhoea. The study included fifty female patients aged between 19-35 years, with a significant number being homemakers. The majority of patients had diagnoses including Bacterial Vaginosis (24%), Candida (28%), Cervicitis (18%), PID (14%), and Trichomoniasis (16%). The remedies prescribed varied, with SEPIA (18%) and KREOSOTE (12%) being the most common. Other frequently prescribed remedies included SULPHUR (10%), NITRIC ACID (10%), and PULSATILLA (10%). The selection of remedies was based on the totality of symptoms, aligning with homoeopathic principles. The effectiveness of the treatment was evaluated using the ORDIL (Outcome Related to Impact on Daily Living) score and a vaginal assessment form. The study observed a significant improvement in ORDIL scores post-treatment, with a marked reduction in vaginal discharge. The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test and Pearson Chi-Square Test were employed to analyse the data. In

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conclusion, this study highlights the potential of individualized homoeopathic remedies in treating pathological leucorrhoea. By compiling a specialized repertory and aligning treatment with contemporary medical knowledge, practitioners can improve patient outcomes and bridge the gap between traditional homoeopathic techniques and modern medicine.

The study's short follow-up duration of three months and small sample size of 50 patients are its main shortcomings. The research may not be as solid statistically as it seems because it was done for a dissertation on postgraduate academic credentials. To exclude the effects of homoeopathic medication in cases of leucorrhoea, the study excluded participants with major genital tract disorders, unmarried females, pregnant females, and young girls before puberty. Similar to this, a more thorough investigation might be carried out on a bigger sample, with more regular follow-ups and the application of more advanced statistical methods to produce more precise results.

CONCLUSION

The study analyzed with compiled repertory of pathological leucorrhoea and found that homoeopathic medicines were effective in treating the disease. The highest-marked medicines showed significant results in reducing vaginal discharge. Compiled repertory is better as it has 10 repertories together, thereby giving larger scope to assess any particular case of leucorrhoea and with an all-round philosophical background. The results support the need for further research on compiling more repertories. The study also found a significant difference between the ORDIL Score before and after treatment. The distribution of patients before and after treatment showed that homoeopathic treatment is effective.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of Interest.

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